

Supporting information

Ion-exchanged UPG-1 as a potential Electrolyte for Fuel Cells

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Fig. S1: Sulfonation reaction of PSU

Fig. S2: Partial charges for Li@UPG-1.

Fig. S3: Partial charges for Na@UPG-1.

Fig. S4: Partial charges for K@UPG-1.

Fig. S5: PXRD of the UPG-1, Li@UPG-1, Na@UPG-1 and K@UPG-1 (blue, yellow, red and green, respectively).

Fig. S6: Interactions between Li^+ with the UPG-1 at the dry (top) and hydrated (bot) states (view along the z axis, water molecules were omitted for clarity). Pink lines correspond to distances lower than 2Å.

Fig. S7: Interactions between Na^+ with the UPG-1 at the dry (top) and hydrated (bot) states (view along the z axis, water molecules were omitted for clarity). Pink lines correspond to distances lower than 2\AA .

Fig. S8: Interactions between K⁺ with the UPG-1 at dry (top) and hydrated (bot) states (view along the z axis, water molecules were omitted for clarity). Pink lines correspond to distances lower than 2Å.

Fig. S9: FTIR of the UPG-1, Li@UPG-1, Na@UPG-1 and K@UPG-1 (blue, yellow, red and green, respectively)

Fig. S10: TGA of the UPG-1, Li@UPG-1, Na@UPG-1 and K@UPG-1 (blue, yellow, red and green, respectively)

Fig. S11: UPG-1 structure highlighting the two types of pores (large: 10 Å; small: 6 Å; water molecules were omitted for clarity)

Fig. S12: PXRD patterns of the ionic exchanged samples before (brighter colors) and after (darker colors) press-molded as pellets.

Fig. S13: Arrhenius plots of the exchanged samples and of the K@UPG-1 cycles at different RH.

Fig. S14: Nyquist plots for Li@UPG-1 collected at 70% RH (a) and 90% RH (b) and different temperature.

Fig. S15: Nyquist plots for Na@UPG-1 collected at 70% RH (a) and 90% RH (b) and different temperature.

Fig. S16: Nyquist plots for K@UPG-1 collected at 70% RH (a) and 90% RH (b) and different temperature.

Fig. S17: Admittance (up) and impedance (down) spectra from exchanged samples at 90 °C and different relative humidity.

Fig. S18: Impedance (left) and admittance (right) spectra of the Na@UPG-1 sample at 90% RH and 40 °C.

Fig. S19: Li@UPG-1 structure along the c axis. Grey circles highlight the pores occupied by the water molecules

Fig. S20: Na@UPG-1 structure along the c axis. Grey circles highlight the pores occupied by the water molecules

Fig. S21: K@UPG-1 structure along the c axis. Grey circles highlight the pores occupied by the water molecules

Fig. S22: Illustration of the main proton conductive pathways involving both the water and Li^+ cations in Li@UPG-1 , obtained from GCMC simulations. The distances reported in green (respectively in blue) correspond to interactions between water molecules (respectively between water and Li^+).

Fig. S23: Illustration of the main proton conductive pathways involving both the water and Na^+ cations in Na@UPG-1 , obtained from GCMC simulations. The distances reported in green (respectively in blue) correspond to interactions between water molecules (respectively between water and Na^+).

Fig. S24: Illustration of the main proton conductive pathways involving both the water and K^+ cations in $K@UPG-1$, obtained from GCMC simulations. The distances reported in green (respectively in blue) correspond to interactions between water molecules (respectively between water and K^+).

Table S1: Ionic conductivity values of the ionic exchanged samples.

Sample	σ (70% RH, 90 °C) ($S \cdot cm^{-1}$)	σ (90% RH, 90 °C) ($S \cdot cm^{-1}$)
UPG-1 ¹	$7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ *
Li@UPG-1	$9.11 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.65 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Na@UPG-1	$1.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$
K@UPG-1	$5.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.26 \cdot 10^{-2}$

*Data at 90% RH and 70 °C from the reference

The pseudo activation energies were calculated by following the Vogel-Tamman-Fulcher (VTF) equation (Equation S1):

Equation S1:
$$\sigma = \sigma_o * exp\left(\frac{-E_a^{VTF}}{K(T-T_0)}\right)$$

Fig. S25: VTF fitting of the conductivity data from the ionic exchanged samples at RH = 90%.

Table S2: Parameters of the VTF Eq. (Eq. 2) obtained by fitting the conductivity data

VTF parameters	Li@UPG-1	Na@UPG-1	K@UPG-1
T₀ (K)	173	226	233
σ₀ (S·cm⁻¹)	11.28	12.84	6.866
E_a^{VTF} (eV)	0.13	0.08	0.059

Table S3: Proton conductivity values of different phosphonate MOFs.

MOF	Conductivity ($S \cdot cm^{-1}$) and conditions	Ref.
Li@UPG-1	$2.65 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (90 °C, 90% RH)	This work
Na@UPG-1	$9.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (90 °C, 90% RH)	This work
K@UPG-1	$2.26 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (90 °C, 90% RH)	This work
UPG-1	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (70 °C, 90% RH)	1
Lys@UPG-1	$6.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (90 °C, 90% RH)	1
UPG-2	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (100 °C, 90% RH)	2
1_Eu	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (94 °C, 98% RH)	3
1K_Eu	$1.89 \cdot 10^{-1}$ (94 °C, 98% RH)	3
1_lp@H	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (80 °C, 95% RH)	4
1_np@H	$6.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (80 °C, 95% RH)	4
$(NH_4)_3[Co_2(bamdpH)_2(HCOO)(H_2O)_2]$	$8.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (25 °C, 95% RH)	5
$[Co(bamdpH_2)(H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (25 °C, 95% RH)	5
Zn(<i>m</i> -H ₆ L ²)	$1.39 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (41 °C, 98% RH)	6
Mg(<i>p</i> -H ₆ L ²)	$9.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (41 °C, 98% RH)	6
PCMOF-3	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (25 °C, 98% RH)	7
MFM-500(Ni)	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (25 °C, 98% RH)	8
MFM-500(Co)	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (25 °C, 98% RH)	8
Gd(H ₄ nmp)(H ₂ O) ₂ Cl	$1.23 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (40 °C, 98% RH)	9
Gd ₂ (H ₃ nmp) ₂	0.51 (94 °C, 98% RH)	9
NH ₄ Zn(HPA)*	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (80 °C, 95% RH)	10
KZn ₆ (HPA) ₄ (OH) · 5H ₂ O*	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (80 °C, 95% RH)	10
Zn(HHPA) · 2H ₂ O*	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (80 °C, 95% RH)	10
(<i>R</i>)-Co(pemp)(H ₂ O) ₂ *	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (25 °C, 95% RH)	11
(<i>R</i>)-Ni(pemp)(H ₂ O) ₂ *	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (25 °C, 95% RH)	11
ZrF[H ₃ (O ₃ PCH ₂ NHCH ₂ COO) ₂]*	$\sim 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (140 °C, 95% RH)	12
Zr ₃ H ₈ [(O ₃ PCH ₂) ₂ NCH ₂ COO] ₄ · 2H ₂ O*	$\sim 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (140 °C, 95% RH)	12
Zr([(O ₃ PCH ₂)(HO ₃ PCH ₂)NHCH ₂ COOH] ₂ · 2H ₂ O)*	$\sim 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (140 °C, 95% RH)	12
Zr ₂ (PO ₄)[(HO ₃ PCH ₂)(O ₃ PCH ₂)NHCH ₂ COOH] - [(O ₃ PCH ₂) ₂ NHCH ₂ COOH] · H ₂ O*	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (140 °C, 95% RH)	13
PCMOF2 _{1/2} *	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (85 °C, 90% RH)	14

*Not pure phosphonate-based MOFs

Table S4: K@UPG-1 ionic conductivity values during cycles

Cycle	σ (90% RH, 90 °C) ($S \cdot cm^{-1}$)
1	$2.49 \cdot 10^{-2}$
2	$2.23 \cdot 10^{-2}$
3	$2.04 \cdot 10^{-2}$

Fig. S26: PXRD patterns of the ionic exchanged materials in pellet before and after of the ionic conductivity experiments.

Table S5: M/Zr ratio calculated by XEDS for the Na and K materials before and after the ionic conductivity measurements.

Material	M/Zr before	M/Zr after
Na@UPG-1	0.94 ± 0.43	1.67 ± 0.38
K@UPG-1	4.40 ± 0.76	4.88 ± 1.05

Fig. S27: Variable temperature PXRD patterns of the K@UPG-1 (a) and UPG-1 (b) materials.

Fig. S28: Flat (a) and transversal (b) view of the K@UPG-1_SPSU membrane.

Fig. S29: ^1H -NMR spectra of PSU (a), and SPSU (b) in the range of chemical shift corresponding to aromatic protons (Solvents: DMF- d_7 and DMSO- d_6).

Fig. S30. TGA of SPSU

Fig. S31: Impedance plot for SPSU at 90% RH and 80 °C

Fig. S32: Impedance data set for K@UPG-1_SPSU at 90% RH and 80 °C

Fig. S33: Nyquist plots for SPSU (a) and K@UPG-1_SPSU (b) membranes collected at 90% RH and different temperatures

Fig. S34: VTF fitting of the conductivity data from K@UPG-1-SPSU membrane at RH = 90%.

Table S6: Parameters of the VTF Eq. (Eq. 2) obtained by fitting the conductivity data of the K@UPG-1 pellet and K@UPG-1-SPSU membrane

VTF parameters	K@UPG-1	K@UPG-1_SPSU
T_0 (K)	233	290
σ_0 (S·cm ⁻¹)	6.866	0.016
E_a^{VTF} (eV)	0.059	0.004

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